

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF TRANSLATION TEXTS IN TEACHING THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract.

Translation texts are of urgent importance in teaching the Uzbek language. Topics related to the issue of equivalence, the role of levels in the emergence of equivalence, and the issue of the method of application are among the current problems in translation studies. The purpose: to identify the problem raised in the issue of equivalence, to determine the significance of the levels of equivalence, to compare the semantic proximity of equivalence between the original and the translated text.

Key words.

Equivalence, adequacy, reference, communication, denotative, expressive, phatic, metalinguistic function.

Introduction

The main factor of culture that connects different nations is translation studies. Translation is the most important form of inter-ethnic communication, and through translation, the works of scientists and poets are translated into different languages, and ties between peoples are connected to each other. The most laborious type of translation for any language is the translation by finding the equivalent version.

The translated text is equal to the original text and should create an impression of unity with it. Accordingly, one of the tasks of the translation is that the translated text takes the full communicative place of the original and presents a harmonious balance of artistic pleasure, content and structure equal to the possibility of the reader of the original. Such a balance should cover all aspects of translation.

Literature Review

Analysis of linguistic and methodological literature on translation issues shows that there is still no About this phenomenon and its components. Thus, L.K. Latishev distinguishes the main and pragmatic parts of translation comretention.

The main part unites the elements of this competence that are always involved in the translation and takes into account conceptual and technological components [1]. Conceptual competence refers to the translator's general knowledge about the essence of translation, its specific features, what distinguishes it from other types of language mediation, the goals and tasks of translation, etc. A technological consultant employs a set of basic translation skills that help the translator overcome the usual "technical" challenges encountered in the translation process and solve various problems. The translator is not in all cases, but the knowledge, skills, skills necessary for translating a certain topic, a certain stylistic genre, etc., constitute a pragmatic component of the translation competence, including specific and special components. does. Specific knowledge includes the acquisition of certain translation methods, and special knowledge is the ability of the translator to understand the necessary topic and stylistic genre of translation as a special ability to fully understand the text in the original language. will be

Roger Bell describes the translation process as a complex process, which includes the following components: knowledge of the language in which the translation is being performed; knowing the type of text; knowledge of the language in which the translation is carried out; knowledge of the field of translation; contrasting knowledge and skills in decoding and encoding, usually described as "communicative competence" [3]. According to the scientist, translation competency consists of 4 types of skills: grammatical, sociolinguistic, discursive and strategic. Unlike Roger Bell, some researchers are trying to group the components of translation comprehension, for example, M. Resas divided the main language comprehension (understanding the original, creating a draft of the translation text, creating the final version of the translation) and a. the number of referential contentions (use of dictionaries, documents, knowledge in the field of science and use of technological tools). K. Nord, in turn, emphasizes linguistic and cultural knowledge, as well as the ability to understand the text, search and transfer information, create a text, evaluate the quality of translation as components of translation competence [5].

The main work in the development of the components of the professional competence of the translator was carried out by N.N. Gavrilenko, based on his analysis, all components of the professional competence of a translator of professionally oriented texts are related to three main aspects of his activity, which allowed his research to distinguish several components [6].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Linguists and translators have different opinions on the issue of equivalence. According to some translators, giving the main content while strictly adhering to the norms of the language being translated is an equivalent translation, and it is emphasized that this is an acceptable situation. In general, "equivalent" is equality, firstly, when equivalence implies no similarity at all, and secondly, equivalent is substitution. For example in Hindi, बच्चे मन के राजा होते हैं (bachche man ke raja hote heyen) "Children will be the king of hearts" or we can translate as "childhood-royalty". In this case, it is possible to achieve equivalence in translation by giving its main meaning without compromising the level of translation. Therefore, in the process of working on a piece of the original text, several variants of translation arise. It is important that the translator can choose the best alternative. In this case, the translator selects individual elements of the text according to the level of importance, which are grammatically and semantically correct. Choosing the translation option with the least loss is the most important factor that determines the level of translation.

It is important to recognize the levels of equivalence in translation.

This has been interpreted differently by linguists and translators.

Translation, as a special type of interlingual communication, is a creative process that requires the main attention to be paid to the meaning aspect of two language systems. Because the basis of completeness of information is the spiritual harmony of the texts of different languages. One of the tasks of the goal of communication is to fully ensure the aspects of the semantic alternative of any image means in translation. For example, in India एक हाथ से ताली नहीं "बजती" (eyk haath se taali nahi bajati) i.e "No clapping with one hand" idiom in uzbek "clapping out of two hands". The general structure and content of the text, which is the main unit of communication, is the field of experience that forms the communicative meaning of linguistic units. The semantic (spiritual) content of the text, which is a complete communicative linguistic structure, consists of denotative and significant parts. The first of these refers to the aspects of the content of the text related to the events taking place in reality, and the second is related to the activity of speech thinking of the creator of the text or speech.

We mentioned above that the content of communicative units requires the combination of all spiritual elements, the expression of a single content, the goal of communication. Accordingly, in the field of communicative semantics, we are interested not in the relations outside the sign, but in the manifestation of these relations in the speech structure through the sign.

J. Lyons, the author of the book "Semantics", which is popular among semasiologists, says that the speaker chooses a linguistic phrase purposefully while performing an action and "expresses the reference in the content of this phrase". [1, 40- b] ra "interprets the reference-not as the result of a one-way action performed by the speaker or writer, but as a type of linguistic activity formed on the basis of a two-way, i.e., "interpersonal action" involving the speaker and the listener". [2, 8-15b]

We also like this approach, because any language activity requires a communication environment, and language communication is a manifestation of interpersonal relationships, regardless of what form it takes. In addition to describing a situation or together with it, the purpose of communication may be to express an emotion, an emotional reaction to the information provided or the situation being described. The language has special tools to express this attitude: a specific tone, signs and kh.z. We are not talking about a specific emotional component of this sign, but about special signs that provide information about the assessment of the entire situation being described. By interacting with the content of other levels, this information is often an important aspect of the communicative act.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that in the analysis of the above examples, we considered whether expressions and similes in Bhisham Sahni's novel "Basanti" are given their equivalent directly, that is, adequately or indirectly.

The original and translation units can be equivalent at all levels or at some of them. Fully or partially equivalent units and potentially equivalent definitions objectively exist in the original language and in the translated language, but their correct evaluation, selection and application depends on the knowledge, skills and creativity of the translator, his language and depends on the skill of considering and comparing extralinguistic factors. When studying the translation of phrases, the translator's skill is clearly visible mainly in finding equivalent and alternative options, because the words given in simple language in Hindi are expressed by phrases in the translation. It was observed that the meaning shifts in the equivalent phrases in the original and translated text, and when the original phrases move to the translation field, their meaning narrows and they take on a new meaning as an addition. The translator translated the similes given in the original in a way specific to the culture of Uzbek readers and managed to preserve the meaning in both languages.

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